

ISic0010

Dedication to Nemesis

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Deae · Nemesi

2. M(arcus) · Gellius · CAD[---]

3. ex [---]

4. ç[---]

Apparatus

Text of ILMusPalermo

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491770

EDR 137593

EDCS 22000854

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7268 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650787>)

Bivona, L. 1970. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelia*. Palermo. At 10

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